

Techno-economic analysis of PtX technologies and their integration into microgrids

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Introduction

Hydrogen is increasingly recognized as a key energy vector for deep carbonization of power systems, industry and hard-to-electrify sectors, driven by growing renewable penetration and ambitious climate targets[1], [2]. In response, a wide range of Power-to-X (PtX) technologies have been developed to convert electricity into hydrogen and other energy carriers. However, many of these technologies fail to advance from laboratory-scale concepts to industrial development, staying at intermediate maturity levels (TRL 4-6). This recurring gap between research and commercialization, often referred to as the “Valley of Death”, restricts the practical application of technological innovation and slows the achievement of climate goals. A key reason for this gap is the lack of transparent, comparable, and system-oriented techno-economic assessments that connect technology performance with realistic operating conditions and energy system integration[3]. This project addresses this challenge by developing a modelling, techno-economic and multi-objective optimization framework for emerging PtX technologies. The objective is to quantify their economic viability, operational behaviour and system value when integrated into microgrids.

The aim of this work, at this stage, is to focus on the detailed modelling and operational optimization of alkaline exchange membrane (AEM) electrolyzer, laying the foundation for subsequent comparative and system-level analysis.

Methodology

The research methodology focuses primarily on technology-level modelling as the foundation for techno-economic assessment for AEMWE. In a first stage, an engineering-based model of an AEMWE is developed, capturing the essential electrochemical, thermodynamic, and operational parameters under steady-state conditions. The model aims to describe system performance in a transparent and computationally efficient manner, enabling the derivation of techno-economic metrics such as CapEx, OpEx, and levelized cost indicators. Simplified representations of electrochemical and operational losses are included to reflect realistic operating conditions. The model will be validated using experimental and literature-based data. Building on this modelling framework, the methodology is designed to be extendable to system-level analysis and to other PtX technologies. In future stages of the project, the technology models will be integrated into microgrid representations to evaluate operational strategies, sizing implications [4] and the role of PtX technologies in providing flexibility and reducing emissions.

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Discussion

The proposed framework is expected to provide quantitative insight into when emerging PtX technologies can become economically viable and operationally attractive. By coupling technology-level models with multi-objective optimization, the project aims to identify key trade-offs between efficiency, flexibility and emissions across operating regimes.

For AEMWE, the results are expected to enable the identification of economic tipping points (e.g., electricity price thresholds, utilization factors, capital cost ranges) that govern the viability of PtX competitiveness and are critical for overcoming the Valley of Death.

Conclusions

This project aims to establish a consistent techno-economic analysis framework for PtX technologies at intermediate maturity (TRL 4-6), supporting informed investment and design decisions to accelerate their transition from laboratory development to industrial application. By developing transparent, engineering-based models at the technology level, the work provides a structured basis to evaluate economic feasibility and scalability under realistic assumptions, helping to reduce uncertainty associated with laboratory-scale data.

The framework also lays the groundwork for integrating PtX technologies into microgrids, where operational role, flexibility potential and economic relevance can be assessed in context. Future work will extend the methodology to additional PtX technologies, including proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers, microbial electrolysis cell (MEC), electrooxidation (EO) cells and supercritical water electrolyzers (SCWE), and to broader system-level analysis.

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